

ANALYSIS OF ARCHITECTURAL DECORATIONS OF MOSQUES IN 16TH CENTURY BUKHARA

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Annotation: In this article, the analysis of the architectural decorations of mosques in Bukhara in the 16th century, the place of mosques in social life, the study of mosques as an architectural monument, the mosques of Bukhara and their architecture are fully discussed.

Key words: mosques, architectural decorations, architectural monuments, architecture, architectural complexes.

Introduction:

Mosques were built in Bukhara as a result of the entry of Islam into the land of Bukhara during the VII Movarunnahr period. At first, scientific meetings were held in these mosques. A large number of people of Bukhara perform their prayers in mosques and participate in scientific meetings, which created the need to build a separate educational center. A mosque is a sacred place of worship for all Muslims.

A mosque is a place where Muslims gather and pray, a place of worship. Mosques are mainly designed for praying five times a day. Friday and Eid prayers are performed in mosques. Jame Masjid is the main and largest main mosque in the city center or in a relatively large area. A special building where various messages necessary for the community are announced, weekly Friday and Eid prayers are read as a group. Musallo, prayer hall outside the city. Compared to the Friday mosque and Guzar mosques, its structure is sound. In Central Asia, the general layout of the Jame Masjid is a murabba or rectangular room, surrounded by a porch on one side, two or three sides.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The roof of the house is vaulted or girder. The size of the porch and the hall was determined by the number and row of beams, sometimes the hall had 1, 2, 4 domes, a row of columns around the porches, and there was a pool in the corner between the mezana and the yard for calling the call to prayer. The first mosque in Bukhara was commissioned by Qutayba ibn Muslim in 713. A local heathen temple was adapted for this mosque.

Near Shahrukh Canal, in the city center, there is a very ancient monument - Mag'oki Attori Mosque. Before the Arab invasion, there was a Moh bazaar in its place, where idols, medicines and spices were traded, and a temple of fire worshipers was also located here. In the last edition of Narshakhi's work, the mosque built on the site of the synagogue was called "Magog", which means "in the deep". Because the rapidly growing cultural layers had half-buried it at that time. The fire of 937 came from the northern gate to the Moh mosque, the mosque burned and completely turned into ashes, writes Narshahi.

The mother-to-mah or Mohilah is built in Bukhara in the XII-XVI centuries. It is one of the oldest mosques in Central Asia. The mosque was originally built in the 10th century, and until then pagans were a worship building. The carvings of carvings draw attention from the ground

level. The mosque was located in the market sold idols, medicines and spices, so it is sometimes referred to as the "Attors Mosque."

The waving Mosque is one of the ancient mosques located near the ensemble of the center of Bukhara, which is one of the perfect samples of architecture. The ground level around the mosque was raised as the cultural strata collected over the centuries. As a result, to date, the mosque is located 6 meters below the level of the city.

In the past, in the mosque building, the moon was a temple of fueling ones. Later, after the Arab occupation, the attack, the first mosques were founded in his place. At that time, the mosque was buried by the cultural strata. Therefore, it is named "atori", "the" attitor ", as the" journey "and the attor market near the attor market.

In one of the legends related to the mosque, it is said that in this mosque prayed in this mosque, but the Jews prayed on the other side of the building. According to another legend, the Jews will be announced that the mosque was praying after Muslims.

Raw and rawful bricks, wood, mud, special "Kurs, stone, and similar objects were widely used in the construction of the architectural monument. The design of the architectural monument: the mosque with the ancient 4 columns. Repairs in the XIV century, in the 15th century, the upper part of the roof is damaged. During the reign of Shaybani Abdulzizkhan, the top part of the building and domes were rebuilt.

Results:

The design of the mosque has a simple solution, inside there are 6 columns, 12 domes, the middle dome is higher, and light enters the building through the windows at its base. The eastern part is occupied by a wide staircase. The head-shaped gable is unusually located on the side of the building. Later, the eastern part was rebuilt. In the appearance of the peshtoki, the arc-shaped deep arch and its unique decorations occupy an important place.

The peshtoq hasham, decorated with ganch and small pieces of brick, is extremely elegant and made with high artistic taste. Complicated embossed patterns are made in proportion to the dimensions of the image. The corners of the columns are decorated with carved patterns, and the garden is decorated with greenery in the shape of a vase.

The architectural monument incorporates the traditions of Eastern architecture and was built in the "Chor" style. One of the unique aspects of the architectural monument is called Magoki Attori Madrasah due to its location in Magok and near the Attor market. The decoration of the building occupies a special place in the history of Uzbekistan's architecture as a high example of the Bukhara school of architecture of the 12th century. Over time, the mosque was buried.

According to the inscriptions on the eastern facade of the mosque, in 1547, Abdulaziz bin Abdullah destroyed the mosque and tried to build a new mosque in its place. But Mahdumi Azam, the leader of the Naqshbandi sect and the khan's murshid at that time, did not allow it, saying that the souls of the great ones who passed through this mosque are present. It is also noted that elders such as Abdullah Gijduvani and Bahavuddin Naqshband gave sermons on the pulpit of this mosque. Obeying Murshid's words, Abdulaziz Khan built a new mosque close to the western side of the old mosque. From the high staircase here, you can go down to the great hall of the Magoki Attori mosque, built in the 12th century, with 6 columns and 12 domes.

The floor of the room was opened and examined, and hoarding materials from the 9th-10th centuries were found. Below it is a wall made of raw bricks, and it was found that it is older than the materials of excavation. The 12th century peshtoq and the pylons on both sides of it

are made in traditional form. The dome-shaped arch above the peshtok door is divided into three parts.

Discussion:

Each part is made of individual small and thin bricks that intersect each other to form a square-shaped decoration. The corners of the parts are decorated with honor, and the intersecting hexagon-shaped bricks are laid crosswise on the top. The carved terracotta frame of inscriptions decorates the upper part of the door and archway, and the walls of the pediment are divided into separate panels. Plant-like and geometric patterns are made on them.

The two sides of the peshtok are decorated with a geometric pattern made of bricks. It was a carved decoration made of ganch on the ground of brick patterns. The corners of the mosque are decorated with a silent prayer. The Kalon Mosque, located in the old city of Bukhara, is a developed and unique architectural structure of the late Middle Ages. It was built in 1121 and was rebuilt in 1514. In the construction of the architectural monument, raw and baked brick, clay, wood, stone, ganch and chorsu baked brick were widely used.

If we talk about the design of the architectural monument, the mosque has a rectangular layout, a wide courtyard is surrounded by a covered porch with a dome. 188 domes rested on 208 pillars. They have a unique majestic appearance, and later, murabba-shaped pillars were installed on the pillars. In the center of the four sides of the yard there are decorated pediments.

The outer huge porch in the east is distinguished by its magnificence and magnificent decoration. Kalon Mosque has 7 outer gates, and there are wide porches in front of the main eastern gate and inside. The bolokhana in the Peshtok archway and the pointed archways on its side are decorated with tiles and glazed bricks.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that in Bukhara you will face history at every step. Each of its monuments, madrassas, mosques, minarets, ponds, avenues, markets and streets are witnesses of the past. These amazing structures, which were built due to the vital needs of their time, together with the old history, the high intelligence, wisdom, scientific potential, worldly culture, and extraordinary art of our ancestors were expressed in the buildings.

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